

Additives for plastics recycling – Need for more transparency

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Preliminary remark:

On behalf of a plastics recycler, the authors undertook an investigation to determine the chemical composition and general formulation of additives used in the mechanical recycling of post-consumer plastics. Initial findings were published in 2025 in the German journal Müll und Abfall [1]. Given the topicality of this subject and the upcoming discussions at EU level, including on the circular economy, we have produced a working paper for all interested parties, which can be downloaded here free of charge.

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Abstract: In recent years, a market for chemical additives to improve the quality of recycled plastics has established itself. These additives are expected to offer significant growth opportunities. The products are very diverse and can be used, for example, for the restabilization of recyclates or to reduce unpleasant odors. There are also products on the market that can repair damaged polymers. And additives are available that improve the miscibility of inhomogeneous sorting fractions. The authors have attempted to find out the chemical identity of the active ingredients and frame formulation of these plastic additives. However, this information is often not disclosed. Even in the available safety data sheets, the entire composition of these products was regularly not included. Only in individual cases, individual substances which are subject to declaration (according to the Chemicals Labeling and Packaging Regulation (CLP)) have been mentioned. However, it is known from the literature that highly reactive substances are used for these products, which are to be added directly to the hot melt in the extruder. Now that the recycling industry – mainly small and medium-sized enterprises – is already confronted with plastic waste containing banned additives from the past ('legacy additives', 'risk cycle'), a new problem is emerging for the future: are these additives sufficiently safe? Possible risks are discussed. Furthermore, a legal classification of the use of recycled additives is provided.

Keywords: recycling additives, grafted polymers, restabilization, compatibilizer, substances of concern, frame formulation, End-of-waste (EoW), legacy additives, risk cycle, recycling privilege, eco-design, digital product passport

1. Introduction

The fundament of the circular economy is based on many, perhaps even endless circles or loops, and is therefore a better concept than the linear economy that prevails today. However, a more nuanced view is required when it comes to mechanical recycling of plastics.

Mechanical recycling uses recyclates from discarded (End-of-Life, EoL) plastic products. Recyclate (plastic recyclate) is a generic term. This includes [2]:

- Regrinds: obtained by grinding EoL plastic
- Regranulates: obtained as granulates from regrinds via a melting process.
- Regenerates: obtained via a melting process (compounding) with the addition of additives to improve properties.

Plastic products are compounds of one or more types of polymers and various additives. "Additives are essential to making thermoplastics processable and to improving end-use properties" [3]. Depending on the application, the share of additives in a plastic compound can be a few percent and, in some cases, exceed 50 % [4] and can even account for up to 70 % by weight (wt. %) [5]. These additives may also include substances that are no longer approved as additives today. This leads to recyclates that, strictly speaking, should no longer be permitted for use [4,6]. This problem is known under the terms 'legacy additives' [7,8,9] or 'risk cycle' [10,11] – based on the RISKCYCLE¹ project (2009–2012), which was funded by the EU Framework Program 7. A solution to this conflict of objectives between increased recycling and ensuring health and environmental protection is not yet in sight.

There is hope that at least packaging plastics and textiles will be less affected and that the additives in the highly specialized plastics in the electrical and electronic equipment and the construction sectors will become less problematic over the time, as the chemical authorities in the EU have imposed bans on particularly hazardous additives in recent years.

Regardless of this, but in parallel with the knowledge gains on 'chemical legacies' expected in the coming years, the regulatory requirements for mechanical recycling will increase significantly. One reason for this is the stricter regulations that have been introduced at the European level for various sectors, according to which virgin plastic in new products must be replaced proportionally by recyclates (substitution). These ambitious quotas are already in force (single-use PET beverage bottles since 2025) or will apply in 2030 (packaging), and will continue to rise in subsequent years (see Table 1).

Electrical and electronic equipment has been subject to recycling quotas for some time now (WEEE Directive [12], Annex V). Table 2 shows the quotas that have been in force since August 15, 2018. "While there are no specific requirements for plastic recycling in the WEEE Directive, plastic constitutes a significant proportion of certain WEEE categories, so achieving the overall recycling targets **implicitly requires the recycling of plastics, wherever possible**. However, WEEE plastics often contain legacy additives that preclude recycling (e.g., legacy flame retardants identified as POPs)" [13].

¹ Risk-based management of chemicals and products in a circular economy at a global scale.
<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/226552/reporting/en>

Table 1: Substitution quotas for plastic products in the European Union

Product group	Quotas	Regulation
Single-use-plastic (SUP) products	<p>Article 6: Product requirements by 2025 (in brackets: 2030):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • polyethylene terephthalate (PET) beverage bottles should contain at least 25 % (30 %) recycled plastic. <p>Article 9: Separate collection requirements by 2025 (in brackets: 2027): Member States must ensure that:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 77 % (90 %) of SUP beverage bottles (by weight) are separately collected for recycling. 	SUP-Directive (SUPD) (Directive 2019/904/EU) [14]
Packaging	<p>Article 7: Minimum recycled content in plastic packaging, recovered from post-consumer plastic waste, by 2030 (in brackets: 2040), calculated as an average per manufacturing plant and year:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 30 % (50 %) for contact-sensitive packaging made from PET as the major component, except SUP beverage bottles; • 10 % (25 %) for contact-sensitive packaging made from plastic materials other than PET, except SUP beverage bottles; • 30 % (65 %) for SUP beverage bottles; • 35 % (65 %) for plastic packaging not referred to above. <p>Article 52: Recycling targets for Member States by 2025 (in brackets: 2030):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a minimum of 65 % (70 %) by weight of all packaging waste generated; • 50 % (55 %) of plastic. 	Packaging and packaging waste Regulation (PPWR) (Regulation 2025/40/EU) [15]
Vehicles	<p>Article 4: Vehicles shall be constructed such that they are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • reusable or recyclable to a minimum of 85 % by mass • reusable or recoverable to a minimum of 95 % by mass <p>Article 6: Minimum recycled content in vehicles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the plastic contained in each vehicle shall contain a minimum of 25 % of plastic recycled by weight from post-consumer plastic waste, of which at least 25 % shall be achieved by including plastics recycled from end-of-life vehicles. <p>Article 34: Member States shall ensure that waste management operators achieve</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • a yearly target for the recycling of plastics of at least 30 % of the total weight of plastics contained in the vehicles delivered to the waste management operators. 	Proposal for ELV Regulation; COM/2023/451 [16]

Table 2: Electrical and Electronic Equipment: minimum targets for recovery, preparing for re-use and recycling, applicable by category from 15.8.2018

Cate-gory	Products	Minimum targets	
		recovered	prepared for re-use and recycled
1	Temperature exchange equipment	85 %	80 %
2	Screens, monitors, and equipment containing screens having a surface greater than 100 cm ²	80 %	70 %
3	Lamps	–	80 % shall be recycled
4	Large equipment (any external dimension more than 50 cm) including, but not limited to: Household appliances; IT and telecommunication equipment; consumer equipment; luminaires; equipment reproducing sound or images, musical equipment; electrical and electronic tools; toys, leisure and sports equipment; medical devices; monitoring and control instruments; automatic dispensers; equipment for the generation of electric currents. This category does not include equipment included in categories 1 to 3	85 %	80 %
5	Small equipment (no external dimension more than 50 cm) including, but not limited to: Household appliances; consumer equipment; luminaires; equipment reproducing sound or images, musical equipment; electrical and electronic tools; toys, leisure and sports equipment; medical devices; monitoring and control instruments; automatic dispensers; equipment for the generation of electric currents. This category does not include equipment included in categories 1 to 3 and 6.	75 %	55 %
6	Small IT and telecommunication equipment (no external dimension more than 50 cm)	75 %	55 %

One problem with these targets is the current quality of recycled materials from post-consumer waste. Despite high technical investments, the quality after sorting and processing is so poor that the vast majority of recycled materials is not suitable as substitutes for new plastic (at the same functional level) and are therefore ultimately downcycled [17,18]. Solutions must therefore be found in the coming years to significantly improve the quality of recycling. This is where recycling additives come into play. In addition to improvements in collection and sorting, these chemical solutions will also be needed to raise the quality of the recycled materials to the required standard.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Materials

The technical literature on plastics provides extensive insights into the stability of polymer molecules. These are long, chain-like molecules consisting of identical structural units ('monomers') that are chemically bonded to each other. Although polymer molecules behave differently depending on the type and number of monomers, they are generally a rather fragile structure. Given the general experience with the durability and stability of various plastic products in everyday use, this fact is hardly known. This also applies to the fact that the observed stability of plastic products is usually not primarily due to the polymer molecule, but to chemical additives that protect the polymer molecule (stabilizers). In many cases, these stabilisers are already added to the freshly synthesized polymer before it is released onto the market or processed into plastic products.

Plastics must be stabilized, as otherwise they age very quickly, lose their desired physical properties, and become unusable. Consequently, further stabilization usually takes place when the polymer is prepared by the compounder for subsequent use in the service life phase. However, these additives are consumed proportionally during the service life. Depending on the amount added, there may not be enough stabilizers left for the recyclates to have a second life [19]: "Although active stabilizer residues will be present in recycled plastics at least the consumed part from the first service life has to be replaced. Furthermore, using recyclates from a nondurable first application, e.g., packaging will not be sufficiently stabilized for any long-term application." But the quantities have to be right [19]: "A well stabilized first application is always a good prerequisite for the second life, however, 'over stabilization' has to be avoided due to limited compatibility of the usual stabilizers with the polymer matrix."

The initial conversion of virgin plastic granules into a product requires melting (heat) and the application of mechanical forces. This process causes significant damage to the polymer molecule and, depending on the type of polymer, can even lead to chain reactions (e.g., PVC). For this reason, additional protective additives must be added during the initial melting process to minimize potential damage (stabilizer as processing aids). This damage can be exacerbated during a second melting process as part of the recycling process.

The sensitivity of the polymer molecule described above is chemically complex and can cause very different reactions. What all of these have in common is that changes occur in the

polymer molecule (shortening, linking, chemical changes), which would subsequently alter the mechanical properties of the plastic. It is therefore, as said, necessary to protect the polymer molecule not only during the initial melting process, but also during the subsequent usage phase. The latter often requires different substances than those used for melting, especially if the plastic products have a longer service life or are exposed to sunlight or weather conditions (heat, moisture).

The need to protect the polymer molecule can often go so far that the stabilizers themselves require additives to enhance their effect or protect them from chemical or biological attacks. Stabilization is therefore a complex chemical concept involving various substances in different concentrations, whose formulation is tailored to the respective polymer types and the intended product applications. Other additives are added for various other reasons, e.g., to improve the properties of the finished plastic product (flame retardants, pigments, plasticizers, surface protection, etc. [4,21]. A recently completed EU project (PlastChem [20]) investigated which additives and other chemicals can be found in plastics. Figure 1 shows that we can assume there are thousands of additives.

Figure 1: Overview of the functions of plastic additives and other chemicals (own graphic, according to [20])

From a chemical perspective, stabilizers for melting, but also for the usage phase, decrease in concentration in the plastic as they are converted into other substances, degraded, or migrate, and are therefore no longer available to protect the polymer. This degradation can lead to complete consumption of the stabilizers (zero concentration). EoL plastics then enter the recycling process virtually unprotected. However, EoL plastics usually still contain a certain degree of residual stabilization, although the composition and quantity of the remaining active stabilizers are generally unknown. Despite stabilization, EoL plastics entering the first recycling loop are often already damaged. This damage will certainly increase with each subsequent loop, even though there is not yet sufficient experience regarding the extent of the damage.

One of the keys to higher quality is improving transparency regarding the additives and compounds used in the respective plastic products and the waste (EoL) originating from these products. Currently, it is not possible for recycling companies to find out which additives are contained in the respective products or waste without conducting laboratory tests. Without this information, it is, to our opinion, impossible to carry out the necessary stabilization of a recyclate. Therefore, high-quality recycling at the same functional level is also not possible without this information. It can therefore only be obtained today through laboratory analysis of the input into the recycling process. Following such analyses, recyclers have the opportunity to gain experience with their input, thereby reducing the analytical workload. Furthermore, they can obtain exclusive information within their supply chain, which can also help to reduce their laboratory costs.

If this information is then available, special additives are required to supplement stabilization, for example. But stabilization is just one of the challenges facing the recycling process. Improving miscibility, repairing the polymer molecule, or reducing undesirable properties such as unpleasant odours are other challenges that recyclers must address. The chemical industry offers a comprehensive range of products for this purpose. Essentially, it is good news that the industry has accepted the challenge and has developed a whole market for additives to improve the quality of recyclates [21,22,23]. The aim of our research was to determine whether these products provide the necessary transparency regarding their composition, or whether they give rise to a new transparency problem.

2.2. Methods

To clarify the question raised, the authors conducted a market study in Germany in 2025 on behalf of a recycler [1]. The first step of the investigation consisted of a desktop/internet

search followed by direct contact with suppliers to obtain technical data sheets and safety data sheets (SDS) for the recycling additives on offer. Subsequently, inquiries were made to the respective contact persons of the suppliers for further clarification of the identity of the active ingredients and the frame formulation.

3. Results

In order to evaluate the recycling additives available on the market, we believe it is necessary to know the active ingredients in the products on offer and the basic formulations. Mandatory disclosure of the framework formulation has been common practice for years in other areas of application, such as detergents – see Regulation (EC) 648/2004, Annex VII [24]. We deliberately mention the practice that has been established in the detergent sector for decades, as it can serve as a model for recycling additives. This applies in particular when manufacturing products that will come into close contact with people (contact sensitivity).

However, in none of the cases where we examined the recycling additives in more detail was it possible to determine a frame formulation. Technical data sheets and safety data sheets were provided either on the internet or upon request. However, the information provided was generally completely inadequate. Only in the few cases where the active ingredients were clearly subject to declaration requirements – for example, CaO, as it is corrosive – was the identity of the active ingredients disclosed. It was often impossible to obtain information about which other substances were contained in the formulations. This means that the substances contained in the products are not disclosed, but only those substances that must be included in the product information in accordance with the Chemicals Labeling and Packaging Regulation (CLP) [25] are listed, but we are not sure for all cases.

Personal inquiries to company representatives provided additional information, but ultimately no one was willing to specify the frame recipe. Reference was regularly made to the necessary confidentiality of trade secrets, and trust was requested that the ingredients had been tested by the company and were safe. However, this does not get us any further, because from a circular economy perspective, much greater transparency is required (see below).

Table 3 shows a selection of the recycling additives available on the market in Germany as of June 2025.

Table 3. Selection of some common recycling additives available on the market (as of 6/2025)

Provider	Program series	Relevant single products and master batches
ADEKA Polymer Additives	ADK CYCLOAID	UPR-001P, UPR-011P, UPR001X, UPR-11P, UPR-011X, UPR-021
aurorium (formerly Ventellus Specialities Austria GmbH resp. IM Chemicals GmbH)	ZeMac	6902, 7050, 8380, 8580, 8880
Baerlocher	BAEROPOL	T-Blend
BASF	IrgaCycle	PS 030 G, PS 031 G, PS 032 G, UV 033 DD, XT 034 DD
Brüggemann	BRUGGOLEN	P30, P31, P32, P33, M1251, M1253; no longer manufactured: R8905, TP-R2090, TPR2162
Brüggemann (Auserpolimeri)	Compoline	CO, UL 07
BYK	RECYCLOBYK	4 4370, 4371, 4372, 4373, 4374, 4375, 4376
BYK	SCONA	TPPE 2400, TPPE 5002
Dover Chemicals	Doverphos	LPG-12
Dow	ELVALOY	AC 1224, AC 3217, PTW, E 226
Dow	FUSABOND	P 353, P 613, E 226
Evonik	TEGO	XP 21024, XP 21025
ExxonMobil	Vistamax	130, 3000, 3020 MED, 3980 FL, 3588 MED, 6000, 6102, 6202 MED, 6502, 6902, 7020v BF, 7050 BF, 8380, 8580, 8880
Kraton Polymers	CirKular+	C3000
Lanxess	Stabaxol	P 100, KE 7646
Nexam Chemicals	NEXAMITE	R201, R202, R203, R305, A94, A99, M992007, M021200, M991500, M992000
Nordic Grafting Company	Acti-Tech compatibilizer	09MA 18, 16MA11F, 16MA13
Raschig		Stabilizer 9000
SI Group	EVERCYCLE	LD-101 S, LD-104 P, PET-102 D, PET-103 D, PP-101 S, LD-1015, LD-6102
SONGWON	SONGNOX	21B, 1680, 1010
The Compound Company	EcoForte	PPC NF 20 769, PET CE 25 100, PLA CE 25 100
The Compound Company	Yparex	42160

Table 4 shows a selection of examples of how substance identity is handled in the referring safety data sheet (SDS). We have anonymized the details of individual products because we did not wish to single out any company for criticism. However, we are happy to disclose our findings on a bilateral basis upon request.

Table 4: Selected examples of how substance identity is handled in the referring safety data sheet (SDS) (as of 6/2025)

Program series (Provider)	Relevant single products and master batches {SDS No. or UFI (Unique Formula Identifier)}
A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product A1: "Mixture"; Ingredients: "Phosphate ester compound A (Trade secret, REACH: Registered): 15–25 %; Phosphate ester compound B (REACH Registration No. 01-2119986881-20): 15–25 %; Organic compounds (Trade secret, REACH: Registered): 55–65 %. Phosphate ester compound B: 2,4,8,10-tetra(tert-butyl)-6-hydroxy-12H-dibenzo[d,g][1,3,2]dioxaphosphocin 6-oxide, sodium salt" • Product A2 {EU-74838, date of revision: 10/June/2023}: "Mixture"; Ingredients: "Polypropylene: 65–75 %, Organic compounds (Trade secret): 20–30 %, Phosphoric compound: 1–10 % (REACH Registration No. 01-2119986881-20). Phosphoric compound: 2,4,8,10-tetra(tert-butyl)-6-hydroxy-12H-dibenzo[d,g][1,3,2]dioxaphosphocin 6-oxide, sodium salt" • Product A3 {EU-74835, date of revision: 10/June/2023}: "Mixture"; Ingredients: "Polyethylene: 45–55 %, Organic compounds (Trade secret): 45–55 %" • Product A4 {EU-09005, date of issue: 10/June/2023, date of revision: None}: "Mixture"; Ingredients: "Organic compounds (Trade secret): >99 %"
B	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product B1: A500-C029-G00E-DU9K, Version 2, revised on June 11, 2024}: "Mixtures; Description: Mixture of the following substances with non-hazardous admixtures. Hazardous ingredients: CAS: 108-31-6, Maleic anhydride: ≥0.001-<0.1 %"
C	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product C1: {Identification Number: 89000736 / A287, Version 6.1, Revision Date: 25.03.2025}: "Substances: This product is a substance. Substance name: 2-Propenoic acid, methyl ester, polymer with ethene, CASRN: 25103-74-6, EC-No.: Polymer, No hazardous ingredients" • Product C2: {Identification Number: 89000777 / A287, Version 5.0, Revision Date: 23.01.2024}: "Chemical nature: Ethylene copolymer. Mixtures: This product is a mixture. "Cristobalite (CASRN 14464-46-1, EC-No. 238-455-4): ≤ 5.0 %; n-butyl acrylate (CASRN 141-32-2, EC-No. 205-480-7): ≤ 0.174 %" • Product C3: {Identification Number: 89001305 / A001, Version 6.2, issue date: 01/25/2024}: "Chemical nature: Ethylene copolymer. This product is a mixture. Contains no hazardous ingredients according to GHS."

Program series (Provider)	Relevant single products and master batches {SDS No. or UFI (Unique Formula Identifier)}
D	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product D1: {400000065513, Version 1.1, revision date: 14.08.2024}, Product D2: {None. Version 1.1, Revision Date: 09/27/2022}, Product D3: {000000021941, Version 1.12, revision date: 09.09.2024}, Product D4: {400000065514, Version 1.0, revision date: 08.02.2023}: "Mixture"; Ingredients: "No hazardous ingredients" • Product D5: {400000003483, Version 3.7, revision date: 30.08.2024}: "Chemical nature: Polymer stabilizer. Components: 3,9-bis(2,4-di-tert-butylphenoxy)-2,4,8,10-tetraoxa-3,9-diphosphaspiro[5.5]undecane: >=90–<=100 %"
E	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product E1: {30769676/SDS_GEN_EU/EN, Version 2.0, revised: 07.12.2022}: "Chemical nature: Additive for plastic material stabilization" • Product E2: {30769675/SDS_GEN_EU/EN, Version 2.0, revised: 07.12.2022}, Product E3: {30769674/SDS_GEN_EU/EN, Version 2.1, revised: 12.04.2023}: "Chemical nature: Additive for plastic material stabilization"; "Regulatory relevant ingredients: No particular hazards known." • Product E4: {30845618/SDS_GEN_EU/EN, Version 2.0, Revised: 08.04.2024}: "Chemical nature: Additive for plastic material stabilization"; "Regulatory relevant ingredients: zinc oxide >=10–<=20 %, CAS Number: 1314-13-2, EC-Number: 215-222-5, REACH registration number: 01-2119463881-32, INDEX-Number: 030-013-00-7" • Product E5: {30769755/SDS_GEN_EU/EN, Version 1.1, revised: 19.06.2020}: "Chemical nature: Additive for plastic material stabilization"; "Hazardous ingredients (GHS) according to Regulation (EC) No. 1272/2008: Calcium oxide >=10–<=15 %, CAS Number: 1305-78-8, EC-Number: 215-138-9, REACH registration number: 01-2119475325-36"
F	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product F1: {SDS: no number, Version 8, date issued: 06.03.2024}: "Substance: 1,3-phenylene-bis-oxazoline (PBO), CAS No.: 34052-90-9, EC No.: 421-510-3, REACH Reg. No.: 01-0000016802-72-0006: >98 %" • Product F2: {SDS: no number, Version 8, date issued: 22.01.2024}: "Substance: Pyromellitic di-anhydride (PMDA), CAS No.: 89-32-7, EC No.: 201-898-9, REACH Reg. No.: 01-2120755188-46-0002: 5–20 %" • Product F3: {SDS: no number, Version 5, date issued 06.01.2023}: "Substance: 1,3-phenylene-bis-oxazoline, CAS No.: 34052-90-9, EC No.: 421-510-3, REACH Reg. No.: 01-0000016802-72-0005: 15–24 %" • Product F4: {SDS: no number, Version 3, date issued: 04.09.2024}: "Description of the mixture: No components classified as hazardous."

Program series (Provider)	Relevant single products and master batches {SDS No. or UFI (Unique Formula Identifier)}
G	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product G1: {SDS: no number, Version 4.0, revision date: 16.08.2024}: "Chemical nature: Organic heat stabilizer and processing aid composition. Components, Remarks: No hazardous ingredients" • Product G2: {SDS: no number, Version 5.0, revision date: 06.02.2023}: "Chemical nature: Additive formulation, Components: calcium oxide, EC-No. 1305-78-8, Index-No. 215-138-9, Registration number 01-2119475325-36: >=30-<=50 %" • Product G3: {SDS: no number, Version 3.0, revision date: 25.11.2022}: "Chemical nature: Additive formulation, Components: No hazardous ingredients" • Product G4: {SDS: no number, Version 5.0, revision date: 05.04.2023}: "Chemical nature: Additive concentrate, Components: Formaldehyde, polymer with 2-(chloromethyl)oxirane and methylphenol, CAS No. 37382-79-9" (Substance is preregistered under REACH [26])
H	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Product H1: {SDS: no number, Version 5.0, revision date: 15.08.2023} "Substance name: Carboxylated Polyethylene, Chemical nature: Carboxylated Polyethylene (Maleic anhydride). Components: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ maleic anhydride (CAS 108-31-6, EC-No. 203-571-6): >=0.001-<0.1 % ○ 1-Butene-ethylene copolymer (CAS 25087-34-7): >=80-<=100 %"

It is clear that there are differences in terms of the transparency of product composition. Some SDSs are completely inadequate, while others provide detailed substance-specific information. However, not a single case disclosed a frame formulation. Legally, we are in a so-called grey area here. It is undisputed that all substances classified as hazardous according to CLP [25] must be declared. However, not all hazardous substances or substances of concern are covered by CLP.

4. Discussion

The performance profiles of recycling additives are known from the technical literature. The available information and open questions on the most important groups of recycling additives are presented below, categorized according to the desired effects.

4.1. Stabilizers

In order to stabilize the respective types of plastic (initially for processing and later for the usage phase), recycling additives similar to those used in virgin materials are employed.

These formulations consist of antioxidants, protective additives for processing/plasticization, and co-stabilizers, and may also contain light stabilizers. Defined phenols and phosphites are used in particular as active ingredients. Usually, more than a dozen different active ingredients are used. The stabilizing formulations for virgin material are polymer-specific. In contrast to stabilizers for virgin material, stabilizers for recycling are designed to be optimized for the requirements of recycling (first loop), according to the manufacturer's specifications and advertising claims. However, the literature points out that stabilisers similar to those used for virgin materials are employed here. Research is currently focused on developing more sustainable and effective stabilizer systems to ensure the long-term stability of recycled materials (e.g., [27]).

Recyclers find themselves in a proverbial dilemma: restabilization is absolutely essential, especially for high quality products with a longer service life (see Tables 1 and 2). However, since neither the composition and concentration of the stabilizers still present in the recycle nor the composition of the recycling additives and the concentration of the active ingredients in them are known, it is not possible to assume 'good practice'. We have been informed that there is empirical data available and that additive manufacturers would also be willing to assist in determining the concentrations for restabilization in individual cases. The situation is even less convincing when viewed over several loops (second loops, third loops, etc.). It is well known that commonly used stabilisers are often incompatible with one another. Simply adding an active ingredient without knowing the residual stabilisers present in the EoL plastic product is unlikely to yield satisfactory results for high-quality recycling.

In the worst case, we believe that risky peak values of additive concentrations can occur in the recycle or in the product manufactured from it. In our opinion, the greatest risk comes from over-stabilization. Suppliers of recycling additives did not classify this as a risk, as the products are expensive, which would lead to economical dosing. However, if over-stabilization occurs, this would cause additives from the plastic (repel reaction) to reach the surface of the product in question. This can even go so far as to create a lubricating film on the surface. The consequence of over-stabilization is increased exposure for users of the product in question. This is of high risk for contact-sensitive products like toys, kitchen products, packaging, textiles or indoor products. Over-stabilization can only be reliably avoided if transparency is increased along the entire supply chain.

4.2. Compatibility mediators or compatibilizers

Even high-quality sorted EoL plastic fractions contain impurities in the range of 10 % by weight. In today's practice, the content of impurities is often higher. It is therefore necessary to achieve good miscibility between the dominant polymer and the impurities. Even common polyolefins such as PP, PE, or PS do not mix well with each other. Mixing is impossible if a nonpolar sorting fraction such as PP or PE contains impurities from polar polymers such as PET or PA. Non-mixability regularly leads to workpieces with poor optical and also physical properties. To improve miscibility, so-called compatibilizers are offered for recycling. These recycling additives are added to the melt in the extruder, for example. This is where the chemical reaction takes place that is intended to improve miscibility.

From a chemical perspective, compatibilizers consist of a polymer chain that mixes well with one of the polymers (e.g., the dominating nonpolar one like PE or PP) in the extruder, and grafted reactive groups that form a covalent bond with the other, immiscible polar polymer. The number and type of compatibilizers and their active ingredients is to the best of our knowledge very diverse, partly because there are many SMEs (Small and Medium-sized Enterprises) on the market in addition to the large polymer manufacturers. The selection of products in Table 3 is therefore not representative.

What makes these products special is their reactive group, which forms a covalent bond and thus achieves better miscibility. In most cases, epoxides and anhydrides are used as active ingredients. However, as they are firmly bound to a polymer molecule, it is argued that no significant migration from the plastic is to be expected. In addition, their reactivity should ensure that the bonds are closed quickly and no active residues remain in the plastic product. However, this assessment is only accurate if no reactive residues remain in the polymer matrix. This could be verified through laboratory tests. We are not aware of any data on this. However, we know from other reactive species, such as monomers, that there is no 100 % certainty that everything has reacted completely (e.g., vinyl chloride).

For recycling additives whose active ingredients are disclosed, it is possible to check, using the relevant EC number, whether these substances have been registered in the EU. Only these substances have undergone a formal safety assessment carried out by the manufacturers. The registration requirement under REACH does not apply if less than 1 Mg per year and per company is placed on the market. We expect market volumes to be significantly higher.

But from a legal perspective, compatibilizers are polymers (graft polymers). In the EU, polymers are exempt from the registration requirement under REACH.² This exemption from registration does not apply to other jurisdictions, such as China or the US [28]. In the run-up to the planned REACH revision, there were also discussions about cancelling this special status for polymers [28]. However, EU Environment Commissioner Jessika Roswall announced to the European Parliament's Committee on the Environment, Public Health and Food Safety (ENVI) at the end of April 2026 that the Commission will not issue its REACH revision proposal (e.g., [29]). Hence, compatibilizers – despite their reactivity – are not, for the time being, subject to the registration requirement under REACH.

4.3. Repair systems

Similar to compatibilizers, repair systems also use reactive substances that react chemically with the polymers in the extruder. The literature cites active ingredients based on epoxides, oxazolines, oxazolones, oxazines, isocyanates, anhydrides, acrylic lactams, maleimides, phosphonites, cyanates, alcohol carbodiimides, and esters [21].

Repair systems work chemically in such a way that damage caused, for example, by aging in the polymer is chemically 'repaired' by chain extension or cross-linking of the polymer chains. What the repair mechanisms are intended to achieve depends largely on the specific polymer and the nature of the damage. It is crucial that covalent bonds are formed with the polymer molecules. This requires reactive additives that cause chemical changes in various forms directly on the polymer molecule.

Since these products are not bound to long polymer molecules, there is a higher risk of migration for repair systems than for compatibilizers. This risk would be particularly high if unreacted reactive substances remained in the polymer matrix and were released from there. Therefore, in our opinion, it is necessary to conduct close-meshed laboratory tests for such residues in the final product, especially if these products are intended for close contact with consumers (children's toys, packaging, clothing, kitchen utensils, furniture, etc.). However, as long as there is insufficient transparency for these products, these investigations are difficult to carry out.

² However, in order to qualify for an exemption from the registration requirement, "the necessary information specified in Articles 31 and 32 regarding substances that may be subject to registration – essentially the monomers used and, where applicable, any added substances – must be available". www.baua.de/dok/8649266, p. 22 (Translation by the authors).

One advantage of repair systems over compatibilizers is that the substances used in the repair process must be registered in the EU for market participants dealing in significant quantities (> 1 Mg/a per company). It is therefore worth looking up the EC number in the safety data sheets.

4.4. Odor reduction

Recyclates often have unpleasant odors that prevent them from being used in the manufacture of higher-quality products. Specially developed recycling additives can reduce unpleasant or intolerable odors. These additives work according to two different principles: absorbers or reactive substances [21]. While absorbers (e.g., zeolites) are to our opinion unproblematic, reactive substances must be viewed critically. The reactive substances used include the epoxides and anhydrides already mentioned.

4.5. Toxicological concerns about reactive additives

In the case of compatibilizers – similar to repair systems and reactive odor removers – both the toxicology of the ingredients and their reactivity itself must be discussed [30]. It must be ensured that no reactive residues of these active ingredients, which are continuously added to the material in the extruder area in the range of 0.1–10 wt. %, are present in the end product. Often, suitable analytical methods are lacking to verify this. If the active ingredients are not known, monitoring is not possible.

When using reactive additives, it must also be taken into account that, unlike when using such additives in virgin material, the chemical environment (polymers, additives) of EoL plastics is less well known. All 'side reactions' that lead to the formation of undesirable compounds (non-intentionally added substances, NIAS [31,32]) can be predicted for virgin material (with limitations). This is not possible with a largely unknown plastic matrix from the waste sector. Even with high-quality processing, it is not possible to say with certainty which side reactions will occur, either for the polymer or for the additives contained, if the active ingredients are unknown (or confidential). These additives therefore pose a residual risk that cannot be ruled out with the desired degree of certainty.

What are the consequences of this residual risk? In the production of new plastics, the potential reaction partners are known and the reaction pathways are therefore better defined. There are detailed product controls and emission limits for pollutants that must be

complied with. Mechanical recycling provides a product that, depending on its type, can have very intensive contact with the consumer.

In summary, we assume that only the disclosure of the composition (frame formulation) of recycling additives enables the control of recycled materials and recycled products and thus dispels the toxicological concerns outlined here.

4.6. Legal aspects

From a legal perspective, EoL means waste is not covered by REACH and materials recovered from waste are exempt from the registration requirement under certain conditions. Are plastic recyclates still waste (→ Waste Framework Directive), or has the waste property ended (End-of-Waste) and the recyclates are to be regarded as a mixture/article? The EU Commission has commissioned its Joint Research Centre (JRC) to develop technical proposals for EU-wide criteria for the 'end-of-waste' (EoW) status of plastic waste/recyclates. Such studies and recommendations usually serve as a basis for the EU Commission to establish legal regulations. The JRC proposes here: "End-of-waste status is granted at the moment at which the output material of the recycling operation is a polymer or plastic that is ready for use in the production of new plastic products or articles containing plastic parts and complies with the full set of EoW criteria" [33, here Section 6.1.3.3]. If a recycled material is no longer waste, substance resp. chemicals (→ REACH) and/or product legislation (e.g. for toys) applies.

If plastic recyclate is classified as substance or article, REACH applies. The operator of a recycling facility would be legally treated as the manufacturer of a good, and that means for substances concerning REACH mandatory registration and, if applicable, information in the supply chain, e.g. if a recyclate or a product incorporating such recyclate contains a substance of very high concern (SVHC) in a concentration above 0.1 % (wt.). In this case, the recyclate or the referring product (when placed on the EU market) has to be notified in the SCIP database³ (<https://echa.europa.eu/en/scip>).

Leaving aside the issue of SVHCs, given the special status of polymers – which, under Article 2 (9) of the REACH Regulation, are exempt from mandatory registration – the registration of

³ "SCIP is the database for information on Substances of Concern in articles as such or in complex objects (Products) established under the Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)."
<https://www.echa.europa.eu/scip-database>

recyclate is also not required. However, this does not apply to monomers, additives, and reaction products contained in the recyclates, which would be no easy task for the recycler, but one that could be solved. Registrations are already in place for most monomers, and it would be possible to join them. Nevertheless, this would involve a considerable amount of work.

On closer inspection, the registration requirement may not apply, as the recycler can invoke the so-called 'recycling privilege' (Article 2 (7). (d) REACH). However, for the recycling privilege to apply, all substances contained in the recycled material must be identical to substances that have already been registered, and information on the hazardous properties, e.g., from the safety data sheet, are available. In the case of recycled materials obtained from virgin materials or compounds (polymers + additives) produced from them (production waste), it can be assumed that the recycled material is identical to the starting material (virgin for the first loop).

From a purely formal point of view, a special situation would arise if recycling additives were used. Provided that restabilization takes place, one could argue that such stabilizers were already present in the original material, i.e. in the waste. Consequently, the recycling privilege could once again be invoked in this case. The situation is different for compatibilizers and also for repair systems. These substances were never present in the raw material. In our opinion, they can therefore no longer be covered by the recycling privilege.

In a nutshell: If the active ingredient of a recycling additive is an important component of the future product (otherwise it would be dispensable), it can no longer be assumed that the recycled material is identical to the original material. So, these additives cause reactive changes in the polymer molecule and are used in the percentage range (<5 to >10 wt. %). Without knowledge of the chemical identity of these substances, the use of the recycling privilege is questionable. In our view, the recycling privilege does not apply to compatibilizers and repair systems.

This means that recyclers who use recycling additives run a legal risk after EoW. They must check whether the active substances in the recycling additives they use have already been registered by others, so that they can join those registrations. If not, they are responsible for registering them themselves, which would, of course, be an impossible task.

The EU Commission recently presented a draft delegated act intended to provide greater clarity on this complex issue of EoW [34,35]. This draft also adopts our legal assessment above that EoW applies to recycled materials obtained after extrusion. Furthermore, it also clarifies that recyclates must comply with the requirements of European chemicals legislation.

4.7. The Digital Product Passport – a possible solution

Eco-design aims to integrate environmental aspects into product development at an early stage in order to reduce negative environmental impacts throughout a product's life cycle. With the Ecodesign Regulation (ESPR [36]) from 2024, the EU intends to expand the scope of ecodesign. According to ESPR, a substance of concern is a substance that meets one of the following four criteria:

- It has already been classified as a substance of very high concern (SVHC) in accordance with the REACH regulation (Articles 57 and 59(1)).
- It exhibits one of the hazardous properties listed in Part 3 of Annex VI to the CLP Regulation (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008).
- It is covered by the Regulation on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POP Regulation) (Regulation (EU) 2019/1021).
- It "negatively affects the reuse and recycling of materials in the products in which it is present".

The announcement of the digital product passport (DPP) is particularly relevant here. In the future, information on the chemical composition of a product in the EU will be passed on to consumers and the post-consumer sector via a DPP in the supply chain. With the product passport, ecodesign thus supports the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability (CSS), which calls for the minimization of substances of concern and the provision of information on their chemical composition and safe use. In the future, the question will arise how the use of recycling additives should be included in the creation of the DPP. A concrete starting point is Article 7 (2) of the Ecodesign Directive [36].

5. Conclusions

In order to carry out high-quality mechanical or material recycling, it will be necessary in many cases to use chemical additives (recycling additives). It is expected that, as demands for high-quality recycling increase, the use of chemical solutions to improve the quality of

recycled materials will also rise. We therefore anticipate a growing market for recycling additives.

The lack of transparency on the German market described in this paper is therefore a cause for concern. An international group of experts from leading universities⁴ and the International Pollutants Elimination Network (IPEN) recently stated [32]: "As the chemical composition of plastics wastes is largely unknown, and many plastics chemicals are hazardous, they therefore hinder safe recycling since recyclers are not able to exclude materials that contain hazardous chemicals." In order to avoid falling into the proverbial recycling trap ('risk cycle') a second time after recycling of currently prohibited additives, it is necessary for the composition of these products, which are important for the circular economy, to be transparent (disclosure of the active substances and the frame formulation). However, this increased transparency is not only important because of potentially toxic substances. For good practice in high-quality recycling, it is necessary for the recycler to know which polymers and additives are contained in the raw materials (EoL) and how (s)he or a compounder must re-dose based on this data. From a legal perspective, it is important for the recycler to know the legal status of the active ingredients in the recycling additives, or to be informed of this. This would be good practice.

The recycling additives commonly used today are very diverse and can, for example, stabilize recyclates or reduce unpleasant odors. There are also products on the market that can repair damaged polymers. In addition, additives are available that improve the miscibility of inhomogeneous sorting fractions.

The current situation is risky, particularly for highly reactive chemical additives used in compatibilizers and repair systems [30]. Small and medium-sized enterprises in the recycling industry in particular are unable to carry out adequate laboratory testing on additives not consumed and unintended reaction products. There is a particularly high risk associated with the manufacture of products that come into contact e.g. with the skin and are intended for consumers. In case recyclers use an unknown substance or mixture, they cannot 'hide' behind the confidentiality interests of the additive manufacturers; they are and remain responsible for the recycled material/product produced. We substantiate this in a legal analysis, according to which the recycled materials have achieved 'end-of-waste' (EoW) status. This is also confirmed by the EU Commission in its delegated act (draft) [34,35],

⁴ Gothenburg (Sweden), Leipzig (Germany), Nsukka (Nigeria), Wageningen (The Netherlands), and Aachen (Germany)

according to which recycled materials must meet all the requirements of EU substance law and must also be documented.

The Digital Product Passport (DPP) could prove to be a useful tool for the circular economy [37] and namely plastics recyclers. The DPP will probably replace or integrate the previous complex information requirements such as safety data sheets (SDS), technical data sheets (TDS), and SCIP reporting requirements [38], enabling uniform data exchange along the entire value chain. If the chemical composition of products at the end of their life is known, they are easier to recycle.

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